

Contemporary Business Excellence Towards New Products Development

Dr.A.Shajitha

*Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration
M.V.M . Arts College for Women's, Dindigul*

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321 - 4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Shajitha, A.

“Contemporary

Business Excellence

Towards New Products

Development.” *Shanlax*

International Journal of

Management, vol. 6,

no. S1, 2019, pp. 12–14.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590357)

[zenodo.2590357](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590357)

Abstract

New product development it necessitates an understanding of the complications of the buying decisions which is usually in the hands of not one individual but a number of people. The business markets requires marketers to understand the consumer mind set. The most successful products in the marketplace are those that know their strengths and product life cycle to form a passionate emotion connection with loyal users and relationships with new users every step of the way.

Keywords: New product development, Product life cycle, change consumer buying decision,

Introduction

A company typically has to generate many ideas in order to find a few good ones. According to one well known management consultant for every 1000 of ideas only 100 will have enough commercial promise to merited small scale experiment. Major sources of new-product ideas include internal sources and external sources such as customers, competitors, distributors, and suppliers. The R&D department will develop and test one or more physical version of the product concept. R&D hopes to design a prototype that will satisfy and excite consumers.

New Product Development and Product Life Cycle Strategies

Internal Ideas Sources

The company find out new ideas through formal research and development. Like executives brain, scientists, engineers , manufacturing staffs, and sales people. training and development are still required to ensure their success. This component is vital because only a skilled workforce can achieve marketing excellence. Ongoing skills enhancement through implementation, collaboration, best practices development, and the inclusion of in-house go-to-experts in various fields of knowledge.

The best training and development programs attack four main groups within the business: leaders, practitioners, project teams, and non-marketers. Each group receives customized training that complements and enhances what the other groups are learning by gearing it clearly for that group's role. the company can allows employees spend their own ides, whether their ideas give benefit to the company or not.

company give various roles and responsibilities, rewards and incentives, resources, metrics, and other necessary factors that will keep the marketing program moving steadily toward excellence.

External Sources of Ideas

The company can update customers mind set frequently, through sales people can meet customers to get suggestions and ideas. The company can conduct surveys or focus groups to learn about consumers needs and wants. the company can benefit by finding consumers often create new products and uses on their own mind set products and putting them on the market.

For examples: Lyzol company introduce verities of fragrances and colors, for floor clearing with low cost. Companies must be careful noted customer input when developing new products. for some products ,especially high technical ones, customers may not know what they need. For example, Nippon paint introduced new paint for protect kids from wall disease.

Competitors

Competitors are another good sources of new-product ideas. companies watch competitors ads and other communication to get clues about their new products. distributors and suppliers can also contribute many good new-product ideas. Resellers are close to the market and can pass along information about consumer problems and new products possibilities.

Suppliers

Suppliers can tell about company new concepts, techniques, and materials that can be used to develop new products. Other idea sources include trade magazines, shows, and seminars, government agencies, new product consultants, advertising agencies, marketing research firms, universities and commercial laboratories and inventors. can help the companies develop new ideas.

Product Life Cycle

The Product Life Cycle concept can be applied by marketers as a useful framework for describing how products and market work. But using the PLC concept for forecasting product performance for developing marketing strategies presents some practical problems. Company manager can carefully watching for product movement of every stage nook and corner.

Introduction Stage

The introduction stage starts when new products entire in the market. In this stage profits are negative because of the low sales and high distribution and promotion expenses .For examples, Well known products such as instant coffee, frozen orange juice, burger, pizza, many year before entered the introduction stage in market.

Rowth Stage

The new product satisfies the market, it will enter a growth stage, in this stage sales will start climbing quickly, the early adapter will continue to buy, prices remains fall only slightly, companies keep their promotion spending highly. the company increase the profits. This stage company meet the competitors.

Maturity Stage

Many products in maturity stage appear to remain unchanged for long periods, most successful ones are actually evolving to meet changing consumer needs. Company tries to modifying the products. For examples: amazon.com new create E-pay for EB –bills, cable bills, recharge bills, gas bill ,etc., The company changing characteristics such as quality, features, styles and packages to revitalize consumer buying.

Decline Stage

In this decline stage sales may plunge to zero, they may drop to a low level where the continue for many years. Sales decline for many reason including technological advances, shift in consumer tastes, and increased competition. For examples: close up paste modify their advertisement, Colgate introduce veda sakhi, and modifys new taste, colors and packages.for satisfied consumer needs. Update consumer feedback can clarify the reason for avoid their products decline stage in market.

Recommendation

Today sophisdate of technologies products entire in market day to day. Business since human beings naturally resist change. Companies must watch their PLC in market every day, and meet consumer update their buying behavior changes, An organization must consciously guide to each sales person , organized training program , motivation speech, and development program. Team member to acceptance and support of the program. Targeted marketing sessions can help everyone understand and accept the benefits of the program in their own case.

References

1. [http://Business excellence in marketing.](http://Business%20excellence%20in%20marketing)
2. Principles of marketing - Philip Kotler.
- Armstrong.